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Title of White Paper	Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in the Canadian Astronomical Society in the Next Decade
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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) landscape in professional astronomy has evolved tremendously over the last decade, both in Canada and around the world. On one hand, revelations of systematic harassment of junior astronomers by their senior advisors or colleagues as well as studies demonstrating significant demographic biases in the peer review process have both made international headlines, illustrating just how much work remains to be done to achieve EDI in academia. On the other hand, increased awareness of EDI issues within professional organisations and governments worldwide has resulted in innovative new policies and program launches that may well lead to meaningful progress. Change is indeed underway in Canada as universities revise their ethics statements and codes of conduct, EDI-focussed committees emerge to advise organisations such as the Canadian Association of Physicists (CAP) and the Canadian Astronomical Society (CASCA), and the federal government attaches requirements regarding EDI reporting and achievements to funding.

This white paper addresses EDI considerations for CASCA in the next decade from the perspective of CASCA's Equity and Inclusivity Committee (EIC). We emphasize that the recommendations below are by no means exhaustive, but instead should be considered in conjunction with other EDI-related recommendations submitted as part of LRP 2020. The goal is that in aggregate, this and other white papers span the spectrum of EDI issues that are most relevant to Canadian astronomy in the next decade.

We make the following recommendations:

1. The CASCA Board should commit to creating and maintaining a comprehensive national database of its members. This database is of urgent importance since it would allow searches for members by other members and by the public, and would also meet the needs of the community in collecting anonymous self-reported demographics data. The CASCA Board should direct funding toward hiring professionals to create a modern database that serves this dual purpose, and that its members can trust and use easily.
2. The CASCA Board should prioritize updating the CASCA Mission and Ethics statements and creating a Values Statement and a Code of Ethics. These documents would provide the basic framework for CASCA-developed EDI initiatives, and should therefore be self-consistent and enforceable; this may require funding to accomplish.
3. The CASCA Board should prioritize EDI training within the CASCA membership. We recommend that committee members complete EDI training as part of their service; Canadian-made training programs that touch on many relevant EDI issues are freely available and their uptake would be a no-cost first step. The CASCA Board should also consider funding EDI-focussed plenary sessions that bring in trained EDI experts at CASCA Annual General Meetings.
4. The CASCA Board should endorse the exploration of a national mentoring strategy for early-career astronomers. Mentorship programs have been successfully implemented in other communities, and would build relationships across the country and enhance support for students, postdocs and junior

faculty outside their home institutions by pairing them with a mentor closely aligned with their personal or professional experiences.

5. The CASCA Board should commit to the principles of the Dimensions Charter, and encourage its members and their institutions to do the same. CASCA should encourage members at the chosen Dimensions pilot project institutions to participate in that study over the next two years and then assess the outcome with respect to its own EDI values and goals.

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Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in the Canadian Astronomical Society in the Next Decade

The equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) landscape in professional astronomy has evolved tremendously over the last decade, both in Canada and around the world. On one hand, revelations of systematic harassment of junior astronomers by their senior advisors or colleagues as well as studies demonstrating significant demographic biases in the peer review process have made international headlines, illustrating just how much work remains to be done to achieve EDI in academia. On the other hand, increased awareness of EDI issues within professional organisations and governments worldwide has resulted in innovative new policies and program launches that may well lead to meaningful progress. Change is indeed underway in Canada as universities revise their ethics statements and codes of conduct, EDI-focussed committees emerge to advise organisations such as the Canadian Association of Physicists (CAP) and the Canadian Astronomical Society (CASCA), and the federal government attaches requirements regarding EDI reporting and achievements to funding.

This white paper addresses EDI considerations for CASCA in the next decade from the perspective of CASCA's Equity and Inclusivity Committee (EIC). A report on the inception, activities and current state of that committee can be found on the LRP 2020 webpage (CASCA, 2019b). Since the Board of Directors of CASCA (hereafter "the CASCA Board") is the body that convenes and sets the priorities of committees such as the EIC, we direct our recommendations towards it. We emphasize that the recommendations below are by no means exhaustive, but instead should be considered in conjunction with other EDI-related recommendations submitted as part of LRP 2020 (e.g. Neilson et al., 2019; Neilson & Lawler, 2019). The goal is that in aggregate, this and other white papers span the spectrum of EDI issues that are most relevant to Canadian astronomy in the next decade.

Recommendations:

- 1. The CASCA Board should commit to creating and maintaining a comprehensive national database of its members.** This database is of urgent importance since it would allow searches for members by other members and by the public, and would also meet the needs of the community in collecting anonymous self-reported demographics data. The CASCA Board should direct funding toward hiring professionals to create a modern database that serves this dual purpose, and that its members can trust and use easily. This recommendation is explored in Section 1.
- 2. The CASCA Board should prioritize updating the CASCA Mission and Ethics statements and creating a Values Statement and a Code of Ethics.** These documents would provide the basic framework for CASCA-developed EDI initiatives, and should therefore be self-consistent and enforceable; this may require funding to accomplish. This recommendation is explored in Section 2.
- 3. The CASCA Board should prioritize EDI training within the CASCA membership.** We recommend that members of CASCA committees complete EDI training as part of their service; Canadian-made training programs that touch on many relevant EDI issues are freely available and their uptake would be a no-cost first step. The CASCA Board should also consider funding EDI-focussed plenary sessions that bring in trained EDI experts at CASCA Annual General Meetings. This recommendation is explored in Section 3.
- 4. The CASCA Board should endorse the exploration of a national mentoring strategy for early-career astronomers.** Mentorship programs have been successfully implemented in other communities, and would build relationships across the country and enhance support for students, postdocs and junior faculty outside their home institutions by pairing them with a mentor closely aligned with their personal or professional experiences. This recommendation is explored in Section 4.
- 5. The CASCA Board should commit to the principles of the Dimensions Charter, and encourage its members and their institutions to do the same.** CASCA should encourage members at the chosen Dimensions pilot project institutions to participate in that study over the next two years and then assess the outcome with respect to its own EDI values and goals. This recommendation is explored in Section 5.

1 Prioritizing the Collection of Self-reported Demographic Information

Demographic data are important for understanding our community, how it evolves, what its needs are, and whether or not various EDI initiatives have an impact. This information is also now required by government in conjunction in official communications as part of the Canadian GBA+ (Gender-Based Analysis Plus; [Government of Canada 2019b](#)) program.

The EIC has grappled with several of the key directives of the CASCA Board over the years since its inception. Among these, ongoing surveys of the community's evolving demographics and the creation of searchable databases for identifying speakers for colloquia and conferences from among the membership both rest on the creation of a robust, professional database for the modern era. This database must be searchable and meet both the needs of the CASCA membership and the EDI initiatives.

Past demographic surveys ([Reid & Matthews, 2007](#)) within CASCA have been sex-disaggregated studies, utilizing a binary formalism of men/women. This approach has been used as recently as 2017, in order to give a binary breakdown of the community, as requested by NRC for preparation of Memoranda to Cabinet on behalf of the Canadian astronomical community. It is important to recognize, however, that such binary approaches to demographics disenfranchise genders that do not fit within this schema, and that those genders cannot be ascribed to individuals by Chairs of departments or other members of the community. The collection of binary data provided by departments or institutions on behalf of their members is therefore no longer a feasible or acceptable means of collecting demographic data. At the same time, the GBA+ ("Gender Based Analysis Plus") initiative requires that, at a minimum, the community report on its diversity in language, gender, indigenous status and disability status in any future Memoranda to Cabinet. It is therefore vitally important that members be able to anonymously self-report sensitive demographic information as they find appropriate.

Recognizing that collection of demographics (and the reporting of those demographics to the IAU and the Canadian government and their agencies) was one of the primary drivers for the creation of the EIC, we recommend that the effort be put forth to get the collection of these data right. The collection should be an ongoing effort, either updated yearly or accessible as a snapshot in real time, allowing the EIC to trace the evolution of the community over time.

In 2018, CASCA utilized an online membership renewal process that was accompanied by member profiles which were to be completed by all renewing members. These profile responses were to be assembled into a membership database from which self-reported demographic data on the community could be gathered. While this was a positive step towards the demographic self-reporting mechanism advocated above, there were several issues with the methodology from an EDI perspective. In particular, sensitive demographic data were saved with the identifying data for individuals, which was a source of concern for respondents. Although the data given to the EIC had names redacted, a properly anonymous means of sampling those parts of the profile relating to demographics was not incorporated into the database. The personal side of the profile went beyond the GPA+ categories (into race, ethnicity, religion etc.), and we utilized the categories used in the Canadian census, but several respondents took issue with those categories. Future profile categories could be well informed by those responses.

Notwithstanding the issues of revising and improving the profile content, the biggest issue with the 2018 database and self-reporting campaign was the limited number of CASCA members who engaged in the profile responses. In some cases, this may be due to the choices in the profiles, but those individuals who commented on the choices were willing to be engaged, at least to the point of examining choices in the profile. There were a potential 598 members with entries in the database (i.e., they were listed as CASCA members and invited to participate in the renewal online through profiles), but the responses reveal limited engagement and reporting. Just 50% of members self-reported on gender (299), and of those approximately 1/3 opted for the choice "Prefer not to answer". Thus, the demographic breakdowns are based on just 33% of the community's input, into only two gender categories (male and female). No entries were made for any entries outside these conventional binary categories, which recalling from above, is the primary reason that self-reporting is now so critical.

Response rates regarding first language (48%), disability status (37%) and indigenous status (38%) were similar or lower. No one reported having status as an indigenous person. The fact that both the gender and indigenous status categories reported, respectively, no one outside the binary man/woman and non-indigenous categories, despite the

presence of these individuals in our community means that the 2018 demographics survey failed to capture the diversity that exists at this time.

Given the cost and administrative burden of the 2018 membership database implementation and the relatively low response rate described above, CASCA's step away from this database for the 2019-2020 membership renewal period is understandable. For the reasons described above, however, it remains vitally important to continue collect self-reported demographics with high uptake. The astronomical community therefore needs CASCA to undertake the creation of a modern, efficient database which is useful to them and in which they have trust.

We recommend that the CASCA Board commit to creating and maintaining a comprehensive national database of its members. This database is of urgent importance since it would allow searches for members by other members and by the public, and would also meet the needs of the community in collecting anonymous self-reported demographics data. The CASCA Board should direct funding toward hiring professionals to create a modern database that serves this dual purpose, and that its members can trust and use easily.

2 Updating the CASCA Mission, Values and Ethics Statements

The Mission, Values and Ethics Statements of an organisation are the governance documents that underpin its activities and initiatives; for a society such as CASCA, they also define the professional standard from which member expectations and responsibilities derive. In the discussion below, we distinguish between Mission, Values and Ethics Statements as follows:

- Mission Statement: a brief description of an organisation's fundamental purpose and goals (e.g. [Wikipedia, 2019](#)).
- Values Statement: a description of the values to which the organisation will adhere in fulfilling its purpose and working towards achieving its goals (e.g. [Arnold, 2012](#)).
- Ethics Statement: a set of principles of conduct within an organization that guide decision making and behaviour, consistent with the organisation's values, that allow it to fulfill its purpose and achieve its goals (e.g. [USLegal, 2019](#)).

These definitions imply that an organisation's Mission Statement underpins its Values Statement, which in turn underpins its Ethics Statement. Documents that specify the rules and regulations of the organisation, such as bylaws and codes of ethics or codes of conduct, are complementary to but distinct from its Ethics Statement in that the latter consists of a set of broad guiding principles while the former outlines specific expectations of the organisation's officers and members in light of those principles.

CASCA currently has a Mission Statement ([CASCA, 2019c](#)), an Ethics Statement ([CASCA, 2013b](#)) and a set of bylaws ([CASCA, 2013a](#)). In recent years, participants in CASCA Annual General Meetings (AGMs) have also been required to agree to a CASCA Board-endorsed meeting code of conduct ([CASCA, 2019a](#)). CASCA's Mission statement does outline the purpose and goals of the organisation but also describes activities undertaken, with an emphasis on the LRP and Education and Public Outreach. Whether or not these aspects of CASCA remain appropriate for its Mission Statement and how the emphasis therein aligns with the breadth of activities undertaken by CASCA at the present time are issues that should be discussed by the membership.

CASCA's Ethics Statement is modelled after the 2010 Ethics Statement of the American Astronomical Society ([AAS, 2010](#)). The latter has been extensively re-worked into the AAS Code of Ethics ([AAS, 2017](#)), which encapsulates both its Ethics Statement and the corresponding code of conduct for members. Key differences between CASCA's Ethics Statement and the AAS Code of Ethics include the specificity with which EDI-related principles and the consequences for violating them are addressed. For example, harassment, sexual harassment and bullying – specific examples of conduct towards others that disproportionately affect some CASCA demographics over others ([Matthews & Spekkens, 2018](#)) – are explicitly defined within the AAS Code of Ethics, providing clarity on the (intentional or unintentional) behaviours that the AAS considers unethical. In addition, the CASCA Ethics Statement is vague regarding how breaches of ethics are handled, stating simply that: “There are several avenues for reporting

breaches of ethics, depending on the nature of the complaint”. What those avenues are, what the basic process for filing a complaint is, what information is required and how it will be handled, or who within CASCA has the authority and responsibility for handling it is not specified. By contrast, the AAS Code of Ethics is expansive on how complaints regarding potential ethical breaches are handled.

The consequences of the lack of specificity in CASCA’s Ethics Statement and the lack of a Values Statement and Code of Ethics from an EDI perspective are twofold: first, EDI initiatives that CASCA undertakes risk being undermined because the values and ethics that they espouse aren’t actually articulated by the Society. More importantly, the EDI initiatives that are undertaken are more challenging to uphold and enforce within the membership because their ethical foundation – and the process by which violations of those principles are handled – are missing. As a result, CASCA is falling behind relative to other organisations in terms of EDI governance and leadership (e.g. [Paleontological Society, 2019](#)).

We recommend that the CASCA Board prioritize updating the CASCA Mission and Ethics Statements and creating a Values Statement and a Code of Ethics. These documents should be endorsed by the membership, and a staged approach in which updated Mission, Ethics and Values Statements are first endorsed followed by the adoption of a Code of Ethics at a later time might be most feasible. It is important that these governance documents be self-consistent, broadly consistent with EDI policies and practices at other Canadian institutions, and enforceable by the Society. Legal advice regarding their contents and structure may therefore need to be sought, which would require funding.

3 Prioritizing EDI Training for the CASCA Membership

Astronomers generally do not have formal training on EDI issues. We may not be familiar with the most recent research on what individual and programmatic strategies may be most effective in creating a welcoming environment for everyone. Anecdotally, many scientists may desire to work towards creating an inclusive environment, but may not know how to do so.

To empower CASCA members with the knowledge to work towards this goal, the confidence to take action, and the tools to do so effectively, we recommend that, whenever possible, CASCA AGMs include a professionally developed and delivered EDI training session. The topic can rotate from year to year and these training sessions could focus on skills such as fostering engagement for minoritized people, bystander intervention training, and reducing implicit bias. This session should be a plenary session to indicate its importance equal to the scientific session and not be the first or final session of the AGM. We propose a length of approximately 2 hours. The majority of the cost proposed will be speaker fees and travel expenses for the professional to be hired to deliver these sessions. It is important to hire experts because most astronomers are not trained to do this work. Trying to do this ‘in house’ in the event that there are qualified CASCA members is also a possibility, although consideration should be given to the burden this may place on astronomers who are already marginalized.

In addition to the in-person training for the general membership, we also recommend workshops to build or refresh EDI concepts for members who serve on CASCA committees. Ideally, virtual sessions delivered by a professional could be tailored to each group’s EDI goals. A no-cost starting point, however, would be requiring that CASCA committee members complete the online GBA+ training program ([Government of Canada, 2019a](#), available in both English and French) when they start their service.

To further explore the recommendation professional EDI training at CASCA AGMs, we have asked for a quote from Movement Consulting ([Cabrera Salazar, 2019](#)). Dr. Nicole Cabrera Salazar is the CEO of this organization and delivers the sessions personally. She has a PhD in astronomy and has prior experience running a large plenary session (“Town Hall on Racism” at the 2017 AAS Winter Meeting) as well as experience consulting with astronomers at universities such as Stanford, Harvard, University of Copenhagen and University of Colorado. It is important to note that her sessions are not about policy or laws or institutions protecting themselves, but instead are about what astronomers can do to ensure a safe and welcoming environment for all of our colleagues. We did not find any similarly experienced providers in Canada.

Movement Consulting quoted around 2000 USD for one two-hour plenary workshop session at an event such

as a CASCA AGM. Two workshops could be possible for about 2500 USD, but they will only be able to run one workshop per day. Using a conservative exchange rate of 1.4 CAD per USD, the workshop fees will be 2800-3500 CAD. Travel and meal expenses will also be incurred, which we estimate to be up to 2500 CAD, depending on the AGM location. Movement Consulting recommends booking their services around 2-3 months in advance. We were not able to get an estimate for the virtual sessions since these costs will depend on the content, audience and length, but there would be no associated travel costs so they would be significantly cheaper. Movement Consulting also conducts smaller, more targeted workshops that would be effective for members of CASCA committees; the virtual delivery of such workshops (at a cost similar to that given above) would be most cost-effective and convenient.

We recommend that the CASCA Board prioritize EDI training within the CASCA membership. The CASCA Board should consider funding EDI-focussed plenary sessions that bring in trained EDI experts such as Movement Consulting at CASCA Annual General Meetings. We also recommend that committee members complete EDI training as part of their service, which could come at no cost. We estimate that a funding allocation of ~\$10,000 CAD would be sufficient to run 2–3 professional workshops in the next decade, depending on the implementation.

4 Implementing a National Astronomy Mentoring Program

The importance of mentoring has long been acknowledged as a key factor in academic success. The current generation of students and postdoctoral fellows expect institutions to have a plan for mentoring them for the next phase of their career and beyond, but we note that mentoring can be just as important for junior faculty, who can find themselves quickly inundated with the teaching and service aspects of their positions¹. This can be particularly true for representatives of minority communities since their participation in committees and initiatives is often sought. Therefore, mentoring can play a critical role in EDI because having strong mentoring programs (targeted or untargeted) enhances the retention of women and minority members of the academic community (Witt Smith et al., 2000).

The EIC has discussed several times the merits of implementing a mentoring program through CASCA. One of the major advantages of such a mentoring system to members of CASCA is the ability to have a mentoring resource outside home institutions, allowing mentees to approach a peer with questions or issues arising in their work life, which can involve personal interactions, without going through their local departmental contacts. In addition, outside their home institutions they may be able to be paired with a mentor who is closer to their personal experience (e.g., family dynamic, career progression) or their area of work (e.g., science field). A mentor in their science field outside their home institution can also foster a future collaboration and/or a future additional reference for a student or postdoctoral fellow. In this sense, a national mentoring program would be complementary to programs run by individual universities or departments.

Although traditional views of mentorship are centered around a single one-to-one relationship between mentor and mentee, mentoring networks are generally more effective and especially impactful for minority groups (Sorcinelli & Yun, 2007). In a mentoring network framework, it is recognized that a mentee has many different professional and personal roles (e.g. PI, parent, person of colour, gender minority, etc.) that results in different mentoring needs. Similarly, mentors have different roles and are able to provide the best mentorship in areas where they have direct experience or knowledge. Therefore, no single mentor can effectively meet all the needs of any given mentee. The solution is for the mentee to establish a network of mentors that matches their needs. Thus, there is great value in a CASCA-run mentoring program even for astronomers who might already have good individual mentors. This program will allow these astronomers to build an effective network and/or grow their existing network.

There is also a significant advantage to CASCA itself as a community. The geographical separations in Canada are such that cohesion in the community can always be improved. The mentoring program would encourage an additional source of cross-talk across departments and potentially lead, over time, to more professional interactions

¹We note that mentorship can be beneficial at all career stages; this discussion focusses on early-career astronomers, but the program described could easily be adapted to benefit senior faculty as well.

within Canada, knowledge of other departments for mentees and increased understanding of other research groups in the country.

There are models that could be followed from other fields of academia or other countries' astronomical societies. There are models of women mentoring women, but we would advocate a broader mentoring program, since the merits are not at all limited to women, and the EIC wishes to broaden the focus to recruitment and retention of minority members of the astronomical community in Canada.

One of the issues with implementing a mentoring system would be organization and oversight. It is clear that the pairings method would need to have a committee (which logically may be the EIC, or some subset of the EIC) to collect the information from interested parties (likely coming forward through submission of a questionnaire, designed by the committee). These submissions would then have to be compared and pairings made according to the identified priorities of the personal or professional criteria. This matching process is reasonably straightforward, although all parties would have to accept that well-matched mentors or mentees would not necessarily be available.

Oversight of the mentoring program is the more complex aspect of the process. In order to ensure the health and safety of mentees and mentors, participants in the program would have to agree to a reporting cadence to the oversight committee (could be the EIC, or some subset of it). The EIC and then participants would also have to understand that there are duties to report at each institution, so mentees discussing issues related to health and safety may not be able to ask mentors not to report what they discuss. Mentors are not trained counsellors and this needs to be understood by all participants. Mentees also need to appreciate the limits of the mentor and the mentors should not be asked to take on the responsibilities of concealing or dealing with management of traumatic or harassing incidents. Finally, it will be vitally important to define what mentoring is and what it is not, and that the code of conduct for the program be grounded by the CASCA Ethics Statement and Code of Ethics (see Section 2).

We recommend that CASCA Board endorse the exploration of a national mentoring strategy for early-career astronomers. The use of the EIC as the organizing and oversight committee for this program has the advantage that this committee, with relatively low turnover, will provide some corporate memory for participants.

5 Dimensions: the Role of the CASCA Board

Dimensions: Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion Canada Awards is a tri-agency pilot program modelled on the UK's Athena SWAN program and "designed to support the Government of Canada's commitment to fostering increased research excellence, innovation and creativity within the post-secondary sector across all disciplines through increased equity, diversity and inclusion" (NSERC, 2019b). The program aims to address barriers to equity faced by people in one or more of the following underrepresented groups: women, Indigenous Peoples, persons with disabilities, members of visible minority/racialized groups, and members of LGBTQ2+ communities.

In August 2019, 17 post-secondary institutions of varying size were selected to take part in the Dimensions Pilot Program (NSERC, 2019a). The participating institutions will have two years to prepare a full application for a Dimensions award (gold, silver, or bronze); award winners will be notified by November 2021. This is consistent with the UK Athena SWAN model which requires institutions that sign onto the program to apply for at least a Bronze level award within three years.

Dimensions also includes a Charter including eight key EDI principles, which all institutions are encouraged to endorse regardless of whether or not they are participating in the Pilot Program. At the time of writing (October 2019), 93 Canadian post-secondary institutions, research institutes, laboratories, and associations have endorsed the charter. The total number of such institutions in Canada is difficult to quantify, but the Centre for Education Statistics at Statistics Canada (CES) receives post-secondary data, either directly or through provincial or regional co-ordinating bodies, for approximately 280 institutions, which is likely an underestimate. Therefore, less than 30% of potential signees have endorsed the Charter thus far. Note that it is not sufficient for institutions to endorse the Dimensions Charter in order to participate in the program itself; instead, institutions must demonstrate that they are dedicated to action with regards to EDI.

While CASCA is a professional organization and thus ineligible to apply for grants from the Dimensions program, it has a role to play in promoting the goals of Dimensions to its members. The EDI-focussed plenary sessions recommended in Section 3 would be a natural forum for this promotion.

We recommend that the CASCA Board commit to the principles of the Dimensions Charter, and encourage its members and their institutions to do the same. All Canadian astronomers should be encouraged to follow those principles even if their institution has not formally endorsed the Charter; CASCA should also encourage all post-secondary institutions within its membership to endorse the Charter. CASCA should encourage members at institutions participating in the pilot program to engage with it and to share their experiences with the rest of the CASCA membership. Finally, CASCA should monitor its members' experiences with the Dimensions program over the next few years to assess whether or not the program has a positive impact on EDI

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

A more diverse workforce is a more creative and imaginative workforce. We succeed in science when all those with research and teaching potential can succeed to the best of their ability. This is where the next generation of enthusiastic, well-trained scientists comes from, and encouraging a strong pipeline feeding our professional community is how we produce tomorrow's fundamental and transformational science.

2: Are the associated scientific risks understood and acceptable?

Innate intellectual ability does not depend on gender, race, or ethnicity. Under-representation of any demographic therefore implies that we aren't exploiting our potential to discover the universe. The scientific risk of not promoting EDI is a decreased return on investment because factors other than scientific merit influence scientific access, funding or opportunities for research. Studies exploring the systematics of telescope time refereeing and allocations (e.g., Reid 2014; Spekkens et al., 2018) and citations and publications (e.g., Caplar et al., 2016) suggest that this is currently the case.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

From the EIC Mission Statement: "Our goal is for CASCA to serve as an example of inclusiveness to the broader scientific community." Canadian leadership is therefore implied.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

The EIC was formed by the CASCA Board in 2015 to undertake initiatives that will encourage members of CASCA (and their organizations) to foster diversity among participants in astronomical research. We coordinate with the CASCA Board, CASCA members, and other organisations regarding EDI issues.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Absolutely. There is no study that suggests that group think or homogeneous communities are more versatile,

creative or dynamic, so our movement toward EDI can only foster good things for science in Canada.

6: Is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

The costs to improving EDI, including the implementation of the recommendations above, are modest compared to the potential return on investment. Scientific achievement and growth are hard to quantify monetarily.

7: Are the main programmatic risks understood and acceptable?

N/A.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

See main text for details.

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